

THE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND THE ROLE OF 'SILENT WAY' IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

Baymuratova Durdona

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Third English faculty

durdonaboymuradova5@gmail.com

Scientific adviser

Axmedjanova Dilraxon

daxmadjonova@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: This study attempted to examine the methods of learning foreign languages. This article discusses the Silent Way as an innovative teaching method in the field of foreign language education. The Silent Way emphasizes student-centered learning with the use of visual aids and discovery learning. This approach encourages students to take active roles in the learning process and promotes a motivating classroom environment. This article also highlights the benefits and limitations of the Silent Way approach, including its suitability for certain language skills and the need for skilled teachers. Overall, the Silent Way can be a valuable addition to foreign language education and offers unique insights into the psychology of learning.

KEYWORDS: *Language, teacher, CLT, TBLT, visual aids, social interaction, discovery learning, feedback.*

Different methods of learning a new language and the role of 'Silent Way'

Introduction.

As the world continues to globalize, it's more important than ever to be able to communicate with people from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Learning a foreign language opens up new career opportunities, enhances travel experiences, and broadens one's perspective on the world.

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Main body: Teaching a foreign language is no easy feat. It requires a combination of language knowledge, teaching skills, and cultural awareness. Here are some key methodologies and strategies for effective foreign language teaching.

1. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)

This is the most widely used method of language teaching today. CLT focuses on communication and aims to teach students to interact in the target language. CLT encourages students to work in pairs or small groups to practice and develop their language skills through role-playing and other interactive activities.

2. Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT)

In TBLT, language is not taught in isolation but through the accomplishment of tasks. Students are presented with a problem or task, and they use the target language to solve it. For example, students may be asked to plan a trip or create a menu for a restaurant using the target language. TBLT is effective because it integrates language with real-life situations and makes learning more relevant to students' lives.

3. The Silent Way

In the Silent Way, the teacher is mostly silent and the students are encouraged to take an active role in their own learning. The teacher uses visual aids, such as color-coded rods or charts, to help students learn the language. The goal is for students to discover the language rules themselves, rather than having them explicitly taught.

These are just a few of the methodologies and strategies used in teaching foreign languages. Effective teachers will often use a combination of these methods, adapting their approach to the needs of their students. Regardless of the approach used, successful foreign language teaching requires patience, creativity, and a dedication to helping students communicate in the target language. The Silent Way is a teaching method that has been used in foreign language instruction since the 1970s. The approach is based on the idea that students can learn a language naturally by discovering the rules themselves without being explicitly told by the teacher. In this article, we will explore the use of the Silent Way in teaching foreign languages, its benefits, and its limitations.

The Silent Way was developed by Caleb Gattegno, a mathematician and educator who believed that students should be encouraged to take responsibility for their own learning. In this method, the teacher is mostly silent, allowing the students to discover the language rules themselves. The teacher uses visual aids, such as colored rods or charts, to help students learn the language.

The use of visual aids is central to the Silent Way. For example, a teacher might use color-coded rods to help students learn the pronunciation of English vowel sounds. The teacher will hold up a red rod for the /a/ sound, a blue rod for the /e/ sound, and so on. Students can then practice the sounds by selecting the appropriate colored rod. This visual aid helps them associate the sound with the color, making it easier to remember.

One of the key benefits of the Silent Way is that it encourages students to take an active role in their own learning. This method emphasizes discovery learning, which means that students are encouraged to experiment with the language and discover the rules themselves. This approach can be more engaging and motivating for students, as it gives them a sense of ownership and control over their learning.

Another benefit of the Silent Way is that it focuses on the language itself, rather than on the teacher. The teacher's role is to guide and facilitate the learning process, rather than being the center of attention. This can lead to a more relaxed and comfortable learning environment, as students are not under pressure to perform for the teacher.

One of the limitations of the Silent Way is that it can be a challenging method for some teachers to implement. Because the teacher is mostly silent, it requires a high degree of planning and preparation to ensure that the visual aids are effective in conveying the language rules. It also requires teachers to be skilled in monitoring their students and providing feedback without being overly directive.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the Silent Way is a unique and effective teaching method that can be used in foreign language instruction. By emphasizing visual aids and discovery learning, it encourages students to take an active role in their own

learning and focuses on the language itself, rather than on the teacher. While it may not be suitable for all learners or all language skills, it can be an excellent approach for students who respond well to a more experimental and discovery-based learning environment.

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